

Influence of stoichiometry on radiation-induced effects in advanced two-phase functional materials for future thermonuclear fusion reactors

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is prepared in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research project No. Izp-2024/1-0162 "Influence of stoichiometry on radiation-induced effects in advanced two-phase functional materials for future thermonuclear fusion reactors" (project manager: Dr. chem. Artūrs Zariņš, 01.01.2025. - 31.12.2027., 300 000.00 EUR).

Summary of the project: Advanced ceramic breeder pebbles consisting of lithium orthosilicate as the primary phase and lithium metatitanate as the secondary phase are developed as the European Union's reference material for tritium breeding in future thermonuclear fusion reactors. The aim of this applied research project is to characterise the influence of stoichiometry on radiation-induced effects in single- and two-phase lithium orthosilicate-lithium metatitanate samples exposed to X-rays. The samples without and with deficiency and excess of lithium, silicon, and titanium will be prepared using the solid-state synthesis and analysed using different physico-chemical methods. Rietveld analysis of high-resolution powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns will be employed to determine the potential changes of crystalline phase lattice parameters and atomic positions. The formed and accumulated paramagnetic radiation-induced defect centres will be studied using electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy. This project will contribute to the Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3) area "Smart energetics" and to the development of international nuclear energy sector.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Influence of stoichiometry on radiation-induced effects in advanced two-phase functional materials for future thermonuclear fusion reactors (Izp-2024/1- 0162)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia, Institute of Solid State Physics, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Influence of stoichiometry on radiation-induced effects in advanced two-phase functional materials for future thermonuclear fusion reactors

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[Arturs Zarins \(orcid:0000-0002-5784-7160\)](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5784-7160)

Organizations:

University of Latvia

Institute of Solid State Physics, University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Influence of stoichiometry on radiation-induced effects in advanced two-phase functional materials for future thermonuclear fusion reactors (Izp-2024/1- 0162)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-03-31

4. Templates

Descriptions

WP-1: "Preparation and characterisation of the single and two-phase lithium orthosilicate - lithium metatitanate samples"

In this data set, the obtained results of various physico-chemical methods (e.g., XRF, ICP-OES, PXRD, Raman, TG/DSC-FTIR, ATR-FTIR, SEM, etc.) will be summarised for the prepared single and two-phase lithium orthosilicate - lithium metatitanate samples without and with deficiency and excess of lithium, silicon, and titanium ions, which will be prepared using solid-state synthesis.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

Data Management Plan | Influence of stoichiometry on radiation-induced effects in advanced two-phase functional materials for future thermonuclear fusion reactors CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 20/03/2025

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

In the framework of WP-1, single and two-phase lithium orthosilicate - lithium metatitanate samples without and with deficiency and excess of lithium, silicon, and titanium ions will be prepared using solid-state synthesis. The chemical composition will be analysed using XRF spectrometry or other relevant methods, e.g., ICP-OES. The crystalline phase composition will be determined using PXRD, ATR-FTIR and Raman spectroscopy. The weight changes, crystalline phase transitions, and evolved gaseous compounds during heating will be analysed using TG/DSC equipment in combination with an FTIR spectrometer. The microstructure will be analysed using SEM.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG
- JPG
- Others

opju

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, we have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The scientific findings of this research project will be useful for all members of the international thermonuclear fusion research community, including scientists of the Republic of Latvia.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Open access softwares; Origin software

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2029-01-01

1 year after end of the project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Arturs Zarins (orcid: [0000-0002-5784-7160](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5784-7160))

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

- Physical access control

The obtained experimental data will be stored in OneDrive folder of the University of Latvia. Access to data will be restricted to scientific team members of the project. During implementation of the project, backup copies of the obtained experimental data will be kept by the scientific manager of the project.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-2: “Rietveld analysis on selected samples after preliminary PXRD analysis”

In this data set, high-resolution PXRD patterns of the selected samples will be summarised.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

In the framework of WP-2, high-resolution PXRD patterns of the selected samples will be obtained using a diffractometer in transmission geometry, with a measurement time spanning several days. Rietveld refinement will be performed using Topas5 and Profex5 software.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG
- JPG

- Others

opju

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

a. 1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, we have not considered re-using any of existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

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2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the publication of the obtained results.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Open access softwares; Origin software

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

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No

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2028-01-01

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1 year after end of the grant project

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No

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No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP-3: “Irradiation of the selected samples and investigation using EPR spectroscopy”

In this data set, the obtained results of electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy and other relevant physic-chemical methods will be summarised for the selected samples after irradiation using X-rays.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

In the framework of WP-3, the irradiation experiments with X-rays of the selected samples will be carried out using a custom-built setup equipped with an X-ray tube. Immediately after the irradiation, the formed and accumulated radiation-induced defect centres will be analysed using EPR spectroscopy and other relevant physico-chemical methods. The thermal stability and annihilation of radiation-induced defect centres will be studied using a stepwise isochronal annealing method. The EPR data analysis and simulations of the obtained spectra will be carried out using EasySpin software.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

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No

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Yes

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No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

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open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

Data will be made available on request.

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